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KESIK PIRAMIDA MAVZUSIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR. 6X6X6 METODI, BBB (BILARDIM, BILMOQCHIMAN, BILIB OLDIM)METODLARI HAQIDA.

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Piramida mavzusi yuqori sinf geometriyasini asosiy mavzularidan hisoblanadi. 10-11 sinflarda geometriya fanini o`qitishda bu mavzu ozgina qiyinchilik uyg`otishi mumkin shuning uchun bu maqolada bu mavzu 6x6x6 va BBB metodlari yordamida tushuntirilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: Piramida, ko`pyoq, tekislik, 6x6x6, BBB metodlari.

Yangi pedagogik texnologiyaning afzalligi zamon sinovidan o`tib, interfaol darsning sifat va samaradorligini oshirishda muhim omil ekanligi o`z isbotini topmoqda.

Bu boradi ancha-muncha tajriba to`plagan tadqiqotchilar pedagogik texnologiya darsining muvaffaqiyatlarini kafolotlavchi omil ekanligini ta`kidlab, pedagogik jarayonlarni ilmiy lohihalashtirish, uni amalga oshirish, loyihalashtirilgan ta`lim tarbiya jarayonini amaliyotga aniq va ketma-ket tatbiq qilish xususida o`z fikr-mulohazalarini ommaning diqqat-e`tiboriga havola etayotir.

Kesik piramida mavzusida foydalaniladigan yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. 6x6x6 metodi, BBB (Bilardim, bilmoqchiman, bilib oldim)metodlari haqida.

6x6x6 metodi guruhlarning har bir a`zosini faollik, o`z fikrini ifoda etish, guruhdoshlarining fikrlarini tinglash va tanlay olish, o`rtaga tashlanayotgan bir necha fikrni umumlashtira olish, shuningdek, o`z fikrini himoya qilishga o`rgatadi.

Ushbu metodni 5, 6, 7 va hatto 8 nafar o`quvchidan iborat bo`lgan bir necha guruxdarda ham qo`llash mumkin. 6x6x6 metodidan ta`lim jarayonida foydalanish o`qituvchidan faollik va nutqiy pedagogik mahorat, shuningdek, guruxlarni maqsadga muvofiq shakllantira olish layoqatiga ega bo`lishni talab

etadi. Guruhdarni to'g'ri shakllantirmaslik topshiriq yoki vazifalarni to'g'ri hal etilmasligiga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. **6x6x6 metodi** yordamida mashg'ulotlar qo'yidagi tartibida tashkil etiladi.

1. O'qituvchi mashg'ulot boshlanishida 6 tadan stul qo'yib chiqadi:

2. O'quvchilar mashg'ulot boshlanishida 6 ta guruhga bo'linadi.

3. Ta'lim oluvchilar joylashib olganlaridan so'ng o'qituvchi mashg'ulot mavzusini e'lon qiladi hamda guruhlariga muayyan topshiriqlar yuklanadi.

4. O'qituvchi guruhlarining faoliyatini kuzatib boradi, kerakli o'rinlarda guruh a'zolariga maslahatlar beradi.

5. Munozara uchun belgilangan vaqt nihoyasiga etgach, o'qituvchi guruxlarni qaytadan shakllantiradi.

BBB (Bilardim, bilmoqchiman, bilib oldim) metodi. Bu metodni "Yangi bilim beruvchi" turidagi darsda foydalanish mumkin.

1-qadam: Doskaga yangi mavzu yoziladi va o'quvchilar daftariga "Bilardim" - deb yozib yangi mavzu bo'yicha bilganlarini, yozish taklif etildi. (3 daqiqa vaqt beriladi). Taqdimot o'tkaziladi. Taqdimot davomida o'quvchilar yangi mavzu bo'yicha bilganlarini aytib beradilar. Taqdimot davomida fikrlarni guruhlar tomonidan qaytib takrorlamaslik qoidasiga qat'iy rioya qilinadi.

2-qadam: o'quvchilarga daftarlariga "Bilmoqchiman: " - deb yozib yangi mavzu bo'yicha nimalarni bilishni xoxlashini yozish taklif etiladi. (1 daqiqa vaqt beriladi) Taqdimot o'tkaziladi.

3-qadam: o'quvchilarga darslikni ochish va daftarlariga "Bilib oldim" - deb yozib qo'yib tushuganlarini yozish taklif etiladi. (10 daqiqa vaqt beriladi). Vaqt o'tgandan so'ng taqdimot o'tkaziladi. Yangi mavzu o'quvchilar tomonidan aytib beriladi. Barcha qadamlarda o'quvchilar bir - birini tinglash qoidasiga rioya qilinadi. O'qituvchi tomonidan yangi mavzu bo'yicha aytilmasdan qolgan qismlari va qo'shimcha adabiyotlardan topilgan materiallardan foydalanib to'ldiriladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati:

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